

*MARKETING OPPORTUNITIES IN SUPPLY CHAIN DEVELOPMENT IN
SMALL BUSINESSES*

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Abstract. This article examines the role and importance of marketing strategies in the process of developing a supply chain in small businesses. The role of marketing activities in improving the efficiency of the supply chain, meeting customer needs, and ensuring competitiveness is analyzed. It also highlights the development opportunities of small businesses through market analysis, effective communication with customers, and the use of innovative marketing methods.

Keywords: small business, supply chain, marketing strategies, market analysis, customer needs.

Introduction. In today's developing world, the role and importance of small business is increasing day by day. After all, small business stands out among other economic sectors with its compact economy, low costs, ability to quickly adapt to market competition, and the availability of processes such as offering products and services that meet consumer demand. This requires us to study the effective use of the supply chain system in small business enterprises, the quick and easy import and implementation of raw materials, equipment, labor, and other resources for the activities of enterprises.

In this regard, based on the Resolution of the Head of State No. PQ-312 dated September 7, 2024 "On measures to improve the comprehensive program "Continuous Support for Small Business", the tasks of accelerating small business processes, financing the development of small business activities, selecting

business entities with growth and development potential within the framework of entrepreneurship support programs and developing them on an individual approach, and increasing the number of new small business entities that create high value in each region have been set.

Literature review. Many foreign and domestic scholars are engaged in theoretical and practical research on the development of small business activities, supply chain management, and the revision of methodological aspects of supply chain management. We also conducted theoretical and empirical research during our research.

Dora Swami Naidu Raghavarapu, in his scientific works, put forward methodological foundations and models of marketing approaches to the management of supply processes and the development of supply chains. Fierce competition in today's global markets, the introduction of products with a short life cycle, and increasing customer expectations are forcing businesses to invest in and pay attention to their supply chains. This, along with ongoing advances in communication and transportation technologies (for example, mobile communications, the Internet, and delivery), has led to the continuous evolution of the supply chain and methods for its effective management [2].

D.Yu.Voronova also works on supply chain management systems, conducting research on the evolution of the supply chain system, approaches to supply chain management in Europe and Asia, and supply chain integration [3].

Another economist, T.T.Khashman, conducts research on supply chain management in logistics and lists the stages of supply chain management, including planning, sourcing, production, delivery, and returns. However, the scientist does not take into account aspects of warehousing, order processing, and end consumption.

Analysis and results. In our country, the processes and development goals related to small business and private entrepreneurship are gaining importance day

by day. After all, small business is somewhat different from industrial production with its mechanisms for combating competition. This provides an opportunity to interest the country's population in small business. In small business processes, due to the continuity of raw materials, the diversity of the workforce, the smallness and compactness of equipment, there are many problems and issues awaiting solutions in terms of supply. Based on this, optimizing the supply process of small businesses and managing supply chains is also important. Understanding the capabilities of marketing in the development of the supply chain in small business enterprises and their effective use is of great importance today. Below we will consider the main aspects of this topic:

1. The role of marketing in the supply chain. Marketing plays a key role in managing the supply chain by ensuring that products and services meet customer needs. Marketing strategies help in the following areas:

- Identifying and analyzing customer needs: Understanding customer needs, wants, and problems through market research.
- Finding new markets: Expanding marketing opportunities for small businesses and attracting new customers.

2. Increasing competitiveness. Using marketing tools, small businesses can differentiate themselves from their competitors and provide added value to customers:

- Building a brand and image: Demonstrating the uniqueness of the enterprise through a brand.
- Improving service quality: Creating a loyal customer base by improving the user experience.

3. Using technology and digital marketing. Today, digital marketing significantly increases the ability of small businesses to effectively manage their supply chain:

- E-commerce platforms: Bringing products to the global market through online sales.

- CRM systems: Customer relationship management and automation of supply processes.

4. Sustainability and environmental marketing. Nowadays, consumers are paying great attention to sustainability. Marketing can support the following areas:

- Promoting environmentally friendly products.
- Creating sustainable supply chains and informing customers about this.

5. Cooperation and cluster systems. Small businesses have the opportunity to effectively develop their supply chains by collaborating:

- Creating regional clusters.
- Efficient use of resources through cooperation.

Conclusion and recommendations. Marketing is one of the key strategic tools in developing a supply chain for small businesses. By deeply studying the market, using technology, and focusing on customer needs, small businesses can achieve success. Effective supply chain management and increasing marketing capabilities are essential for the success of small businesses. From planning and forecasting to managing supplier relationships and mitigating risk, every stage of the supply chain offers opportunities for optimization. Thanks to advances in technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and automation, even small businesses can increase efficiency, visibility, and sustainability in their supply chains.

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